

YouTube Classroom Channel As An Alternative Media for Independent Learning

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Social media (socmed) websites is the signature of Web 2.0, an era where internet users provide websites' content--photos, videos, news, etc--and share it with people around the world through its network. Three of the popular socmeds are Vimeo, Slideshare, Blogspot, and YouTube, each with its own functions and characteristics. Besides sharing videos, photos, and docs, socmed apparently provides another potential for teachers to interact with their students beyond the constraint of time and space. Since socmeds are user generated websites, teachers and lecturers can use them to keep students engaged in their study by sharing lesson materials in the form of podcasts, videocasts, or docs.

One of the prominent socmeds for teaching and learning is YouTube. Among 5 million videos in its collection, there are thousands of video podcasts (tutorials) for independent learning which are free to watch and easy to download. Those videos, made by common people and experts, cover topics ranging from how to bake brownies to English pronunciation. To support his teaching, the researcher often use videos from YT in classroom (Douglas (2001) and Harmer (2001)) at which students responds to it well. The experience of using videos downloaded from YT that drove the research on the effectiveness of YT channel as an alternative media for Public Speaking course.

Public Speaking Class

At English Department of STBA LIA Jakarta, Public Speaking is a non-mandatory course offered to students sitting on 5th semester. In this course, students learn the extensive art of public in the form of oral speech, ranging from welcome speech to farewell speech. As part of learning, students get regular assignment of creating their own public speaking.

In terms of classroom activities, Public Speaking is carried out in a conventional way in which the class lecturer, as the source of information, controls all the teaching and learning activities inside classroom while students depend on textbook course syllabus. However, outside classroom, students do not have other sources of learning besides their textbooks. Even if they can use internet to find extra learning source, they do not know where to look for. When students have a speech assignment, they will perform in front of their peers and lecturer without having a chance to review their own performance. If they get feedbacks from the lecturer and peers, they seldom understand what area that really needs improvement.

With that condition in mind and popularity of YT, it was very interesting to see if classroom channel at YT could assist students in their study at Public Speaking course and improve their speech performance. Additionally, the research wanted to find out students' responds toward socmed approach in supporting their learning.

Classroom YouTube Channel

The theoretical framework for this research is grounded on Vigotsky's work, a proponent of Constructivism ((www.Learningtheories.com). On its ground, learning is an active continuous process which students develop independently with the purpose of discovering the most effective learning strategy which can increase their knowledge and competency. To be able to achieve that, students need feedbacks about their works and they also need to review their own work. Therefore, using YouTube channel was expected to develop and enhance the cognitive, metacognitive, and affective areas of students' learning strategies.

For the first step, a classroom YT channel, titled *materikuliaah*, was created. The purpose of which is to put video records of students' speech in classroom, to provide supplementary materials in the form of video podcasts and to collect videos, from YT collection, related to the art of Public Speaking. To ease students' effort in exploring the video collection at *materikuliaah*, playlists were created to group videos into five categories--Videocasts, Samples of 3 different categories of Speech, Public Speaking Tips, and Students Speech Video.

After that, students were encouraged to create their own YT accounts and subscribed to *materikuliaah*. By having an account at YT, students would create network among themselves thus allowing them to comment on the videos in classroom channel. The comments can be feedbacks to students performance and they could also lead to a discussion. This is inline with Constructivism concept (Tait: <http://www.cti.ac.uk/publ/actlea>) who states that, in the beginning phase, students actively do reflection of a concept that they learn. Additionally, the Like and Dislike buttons would enable the class to see which speech performance was favored by members of the class. Indirectly, it would provide a sense of competition among students to improve their speech skills and to push them to give their best presentation.

Classroom Implementation

Students responds to classroom channel on YouTube were mixed in the beginning. Some of them were enthusiastic but some were not sure. For them, the idea of having their speech performance being recorded and shared though internet were interesting but having the videos publicly open was not comforting. They thought it would be embarassing if people watched their less perfect speech. However, the researcher erased those thoughts by explaining that students would get plenty of benefits from the YT channel as elaborated previously.

At the end of the semester, the lecturer distributed questionnaires to find out students responses about using YT channel, materikuliah, to support students in their independent and active learning. The result of the questionnaires showed that the classroom channel really supported them in Public Speaking course. The samples of public speaking videos also helped them in doing their assignments and the video records of their speech assisted them in reflecting their performance. It also appeared that students speech got better in each assignment as shown by the score chart below.

On the other hand, there were some expectations that did not come about with this YouTube classroom channel. First, students feedbacks on their friends' speech were praises. It seemed they were not interested to give constructive comments which might help their peers to improve. The expectation of polling the best speech for each assignment did not happen because everyone liked his/her own videos and seldom liked others' video. Through informal interview, the researcher learned that students did not feel comfortable with commenting their friends' weakness and voting for the best speech. Furthermore, they believed that everyone in the class had done his/her best and that effort should be appreciated. Other reasons of not giving comments and votes was slow internet connection and students' preference of talking about it face-to-face.

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